

IGNATIAN

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL FOR
MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH

www.icceph.com

ISSN 2984-9942

FACTORS AFFECTING THE BEHAVIORAL INTENTION OF ENGINEERING STUDENTS IN UTILIZING GOOGLE CLASSROOM IN STATISTICS

Aura Marie B. Novesteras

College of Engineering, Quezon City University, Quezon City, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10640802>

ABSTRACT

This study intends to examine engineering students' behavioral intentions when utilizing Google Classroom in attending Statistics class. The Technology Acceptance Model was utilized to measure the variables that affect the behavioral intentions of the users and the level of satisfaction concerning Google Classroom utilization as an educational management system in Statistics class. The behavioral intentions of the users are greatly influenced by perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. The degree to which people believe that using a specific technology would be easy and simple is known as perceived ease of use. Conversely, perceived usefulness is associated with users' perceptions of how much technology boosts their productivity and helps them accomplish their academic activities. Results of the study revealed that users of Google Classroom are "very satisfied" in terms of perceived ease of use. The Google Classroom's intuitive interface gives students flexibility in their education and makes sure that information is accessible when needed. In terms of perceived usefulness, data revealed that users are "satisfied" with utilizing the Google Classroom. Students in particular believe that this online learning platform enhances their academic activities and improves their educational experience.

Keywords: *Google Classroom, Higher Education, Behavioral Intention, Technology Acceptance Model, Statistics*

INTRODUCTION

The way that technology is integrated into the classroom has fundamentally changed the idea of traditional learning. This is because of creative teaching strategies that prioritize the needs of the students to meet educational objectives (Hwang et al., 2015). Blended learning is the integration of online and face-to-face instruction. It is an educational practice that combines conventional classroom instruction with online components. This technology integration has been made possible with the help of Google Classroom. According to Northey et al. (2018), technology helps increase student involvement, which is essential to achieving the intended learning objectives. Under this approach, teachers create, manage, and share digital learning resources like quizzes, assignments, and resources using the Google management systems that are stored in a cloud environment. With the help of this online platform, teachers can save time and paper while maintaining classroom organization. This has resulted in a new trend in education where increased technological use is considered an acceptable medium of instruction. According to Keengwe & Georgina (2012), these technological Advancements have led to significant changes in the delivery of education and are regarded as a vital component of blended learning (Rasheed et al., 2020). A study by Azhar and Iqbal (2018) emphasized that collaborative learning through assignments in Google Classroom was seen to be a very powerful strategy for raising student engagement. In addition, another advantage of Google Classroom is the ease of communication which allows professors and students to communicate outside of the classroom resulting in improved communication in general (Azhar & Iqbal, 2018). Users of Google Classroom agreed that it is user-friendly, and that extensive training is not necessary in manipulating it (Santos, 2021). In the study of Mafa (2018), students found Google Classroom to be exciting when it came to the teaching and learning process. Students also believed that it facilitates interaction, communication, and ease download of delivery of instruction. Although Google Classroom offers a variety of e-learning experiences, users find it beneficial because learning materials can be shared and accessed with ease (Alim et al., 2019). Additionally, using Google Classroom fosters the development of problem-solving abilities, and higher-order thinking abilities which are more appealing in this era of computers (Shaharaneet et al., 2016).

The widely accepted theory of acceptance, known as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), explains users' acceptance of technology by examining the behaviors that influence them. Users' utilization of technology is influenced by two factors: perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. These two elements work together which affects the intention of the user to utilize and adopt the technology (Saadé & Bahli, 2005). The perceived ease of use occurs when a user feels comfortable and doesn't need to exert any effort to use the technology (Wijaya, 2016). Perceived usefulness, according to Omar et al., (2019) is an indicator of utilizing technology to enhance performance at work. Perceived usefulness in this study is associated with using Google Classroom and how it may influence the user's subjective perception of Google Classroom based on the Technology Acceptance Model. According to Zuñiga-Tonio's (2021) study, the majority of students agreed that Google Classroom offers accessibility, utility, and user satisfaction,

as measured by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Through the use of Google Classroom, users have discovered that the platform facilitates lighter and faster work in terms of perceived usability, the respondents appreciated the fact that they didn't need to rush to school just to beat the deadline (Kumar et al., 2020). Moreover, turning in assignments eliminates the need for them to print their outputs. The quality of information was found to be the main factor influencing user intention and satisfaction with the use of e-learning, as motivation and intention had a favorable effect perceived usability of e-learning (Mohammadi, 2015).

In this study, the Technology Acceptance Model was utilized to analyze the engineering students' behavioral intention and level of satisfaction when using Google Classroom in their statistics class concerning perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness.

Research Questions

To critically examine the behavioral intention and level of satisfaction of engineering students, this study specifically addresses the following:

1. What is the level of satisfaction of the engineering students in utilizing the Google Classroom in terms of perceived ease of use?
2. What is the level of satisfaction of the engineering students in utilizing the Google Classroom in terms of perceived usefulness?
3. What is the level of behavioral intention among engineering students regarding the use of Google Classroom?

Theoretical Framework

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) reflects the users' intention to utilize Google Classroom based on two variables such as perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. In this study, the degree to which a user perceives utilizing Google Classroom will be effortless is known as Perceived Ease of Use. The simplicity of the system, ease of instructions, and the design of the user interface contribute to users' more favorable acceptance of technology while the degree to which the user perceives that utilizing Google Classroom would enhance their academic performance is considered as perceived usefulness. Users' perception that utilizing Google Classroom will help them achieve their academic goals, they are more inclined to adopt and utilize it (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Technology Acceptance Model of Google Classroom Utilization

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to assess the level of satisfaction of students in adopting and utilizing Google Classroom in Statistics subject in terms of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. The study's sample consisted of Quezon City University industrial engineering students taking statistics courses for the School Year 2022-2023.

An adopted modified survey instrument was utilized in this study. The instrument had undergone evaluation by experts in the field of Industrial Engineering. With the help of the professor's assistance, a survey questionnaire was employed via Google Forms to 257 respondents. All the information needed for the study was gathered by the researcher and tallied. A five-point Likert scale was employed to measure the level of acceptance of users having a verbal interpretation of "very satisfied" to "unsatisfied," ranging from 5 to 1, was used.

5:00-4.21	Very Satisfied
4.20-3.41	Satisfied
3.40-2.61	Neutral
2.60-1.81	Slightly Satisfied
1.80-1.00	Unsatisfied

RESULTS

1. Level of Satisfaction of the Engineering Students in Adopting the Google Classroom in Terms of Perceived Ease of Use

Table 1 presents the users' level of satisfaction with the utilization of Google Classroom in a Statistics class. The average mean of 4.52, indicating a "very satisfied" interpretation. The top-ranking factor contributing to "very satisfied" verbal interpretation got a mean score of 4.81, "Google Classroom easily delivers the information I need". The second rank revealed a mean of 4.69, "Google Classroom enables users to interact with the

platform on a variety of devices”. Followed by a mean of 4.50, “Google Classroom has a simple interface for easy navigation”. The fourth rank uncovered a mean of 4.31, “The instructional materials are conveniently accessible through Google Classroom” and last but not least have a mean of 4.27, “My performance is easy to monitor in Google Classroom”. Overall, respondents express a high level of satisfaction with Google Classroom in the context of their Statistics class.

Table 1 Respondent's Level of Satisfaction in Using Google Classroom in Terms of Perceived Ease of Use

a. Perceived Ease of Use	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
1. Google Classroom easily delivers the information I need.	4.81	1 st	Very Satisfied
2. The instructional materials are conveniently accessible through Google Classroom.	4.31	4 th	Very Satisfied
3. My performance is easy to monitor in Google Classroom.	4.27	5 th	Very Satisfied
4. Google Classroom has a simple interface for easy navigation.	4.50	3 rd	Very Satisfied
5. Google Classroom enables users to interact with the platform on a variety of devices.	4.69	2 nd	Very Satisfied
Average Mean	4.52		Very Satisfied

In terms of perceived ease of use, Google Classroom has attained high satisfaction among users in their statistics class. The easy access to information and instructional materials contributes to a positive user perception. The platform's adaptability to many devices—including desktops, laptops, and mobile devices complements its ease of use, enabling an easy educational process. This is favorable to the study of Wijaya (2016) that the user feels comfortable accessing the system when there is no need to exert too much effort. Furthermore, Google Classroom's user-friendly interface and convenient access to learning resources make navigating the platform effortless. The monitoring function for users, which provides students with progress reports on their academic work, is another noteworthy feature. In terms of providing a simple and efficient learning environment for statistics students, Google Classroom performs admirably overall.

2. Level of Satisfaction of the Engineering Students in Adopting the Google Classroom in Terms of Perceived Usefulness

The user's level of satisfaction regarding the perceived usefulness of Google Classroom in a Statistics class was shown in Table 2, revealing an average mean of 4.32 and a verbal interpretation of "very satisfied". "Google Classroom facilitates accomplishing more tasks and assignments received a "very satisfied" interpretation ranking as first place.

Followed by “Google Classroom enhances my learning experience” with a mean of 4.49. The third rank is “Google Classroom makes my learning easier and simpler” revealed a mean of 4.40. “Google Classroom facilitates my interactions with the class” with a mean of 4.13 was fourth in the rank. The fifth rank got a mean of 4.06 states that “Google Classroom helps me get higher test results”. Overall, users express a positive level of satisfaction with the perceived usefulness of Google Classroom in their Statistics class.

Table 2 Respondent's Level of Satisfaction in Using Google Classroom in Terms of Perceived Usefulness

b. Perceived Usefulness	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
1. Google Classroom helps me get higher test results.	4.06	5 th	Satisfied
2. Google Classroom facilitates accomplishing more tasks and assignments.	4.53	1 st	Very Satisfied
3. Google Classroom makes my learning easier and simpler.	4.40	3 rd	Very Satisfied
4. Google Classroom enhances my learning experience.	4.49	2 nd	Very Satisfied
5. Google Classroom facilitates my interactions with the class.	4.13	4 th	Satisfied
Average Mean	4.32		Very Satisfied

For engineering students, Google Classroom has become an indispensable tool in their academic path, as it facilitates the completion of activities and assignments. The study of Mafa (2018) found that students are excited in attending the class using Google Classroom platform. Meanwhile, according to Shaharane et al. (2016) using Google Classroom fosters the development of problem-solving abilities of students as well as their higher-order thinking abilities. The efficiency of the platform facilitates a better student association in addition to a simplified learning process. Furthermore, Google Classroom is essential for improving users' academic performance by assisting them in obtaining better test scores, which are crucial for engineering education.

3. Level of Behavioral Intention Among Engineering Students Regarding the Use of Google Classroom in Statistics

Table 3 presents the respondent's level of behavioral intention to use Google Classroom in attending statistics class. The study disclosed that respondents are very satisfied with an average mean of 4.74. The highest rank got a mean of 4.83 which states that “I intend to use Google Classroom as part of my learning experience “ from which Students use Google Classroom as part of their learning experience. The second rank revealed a mean of 4.80, “It Is worth to recommend Google Classroom to our students “. Data uncovered that it is beneficial to suggest the use of Google Classroom to actively interact with the class. Followed by the third rank with a mean of 4.73, “I plan to use Google Classroom in the future “ which means that students intend to utilize Google Classroom every day to

meet educational goals. A mean of 4.69 ranks as the fourth “I like the idea of integrating Google Classroom into the classroom setting”. Meanwhile, last of the rank got a mean of 4.67, “Using Google Classroom is interesting”. As a new trend in blended learning, students think it's a good idea that Google Classroom has been incorporated into the classroom. For the students, Google Classroom is interesting because it aids interaction, and better communication, and provides an easy delivery of instruction among them.

Table 3 Respondent's Level of Behavioral Intention to Use Google Classroom

c. Behavioral Intention to Use	Mean	Rank	Interpretation
1. I intend to use Google Classroom as part of my learning experience.	4.83	1 st	Very Satisfied
2. I plan to use Google Classroom in the future.	4.73	3 rd	Very Satisfied
3. I like the idea of integrating Google Classroom into the classroom setting.	4.69	4 th	Very Satisfied
4. It Is worth to recommend Google Classroom to our students.	4.80	2 nd	Very Satisfied
5. Using Google Classroom is interesting.	4.67	5 th	Very Satisfied
Average Mean	4.74		Very Satisfied

Based on the results, students are very satisfied because the integration of Google Classroom in Statistics class resulted in a pleasing experience that the students find beneficial for active class interaction. They expect to utilize Google Classroom daily to learn the basics of data gathering, meaningful analysis, and interpretation of statistical findings. The integration of Google Classroom into the classroom considered a new trend in blended learning, is viewed positively by students. They find Google Classroom interesting as it facilitates interaction, improves communication, and simplifies the delivery of instructions among them.

DISCUSSION

Regarding the use of Google Classroom particularly in statistics classes, Google Classroom is recognized for its user-friendly and accessibility. Users are satisfied with how easy it is to use and how convenient it is to obtain information. This result is favorable to the study of Mohammadi (2015) that the context of e-learning is significantly influenced by the quality of the information they can get especially in connection to learning. The information provided through e-learning platforms is of good quality and users are more inclined to be motivated and pleased with their educational experiences. The second factor contributing to the perceived ease of use of Google Classroom is its portability that users can easily interact with their statistics class using different kinds of devices allowing them to conveniently participate in their educational activities regardless of their location.

This is indicated in the study of Zuñiga-Tonio (2021), most students harmonized that Google Classroom provides accessibility, usefulness, and pleasure. Meanwhile, Google Classroom's easy navigation is supported by the study of Santos (2021) that extensive training is not necessary to manipulate it. In addition, users find Google Classroom useful because learning materials are easily shared and accessed (Alim et al., 2019).

The respondent's level of satisfaction in using Google Classroom in terms of perceived usefulness revealed a very satisfied interpretation because student engagement helps accomplish more tasks. According to Mafa's (2018) study, students believed Google Classroom facilitates interaction. Google Classroom enhances students' learning experience. Omar et al., (2019) expressed a favorable view that performance at work is enhanced by technology utilization and according to Northey et al. (2018), technology helps increase student involvement, which is essential to achieving the intended learning objectives. Furthermore, Google Classroom makes student's learning easier and simpler. Kumar et al. (2020) view this study favorably, that users of Google Classroom see that the platform resulted a lighter and faster work while not rushing to school without the need to hurry to beat the deadline. Moreover, Google Classroom facilitates student interactions as highlighted in the study of Azhar and Iqbal (2018) the positive aspect of Google Classroom enabling student interactions, particularly emphasizing the effectiveness of collaborative learning through assignments in enhancing student engagement helps them get higher test results.

The respondents' behavioral intention to use Google Classroom was interpreted as very satisfied. students intend to use Google Classroom as part of their learning experience is the highest factor that contributes to the behavioral intention to use Google Classroom because these creative teaching strategies prioritize the needs of the students to meet educational objectives (Hwang et al., 2015). It is worth recommending Google Classroom to other students. Likewise, students plan to use Google Classroom in the upcoming. Students like the idea of integrating Google Classroom into their statistics class because it fosters the development of problem-solving abilities and higher-order thinking abilities (Shaharane et al., 2016). Using Google Classroom is interesting and considered an acceptable medium of instruction which agrees with Northey et al. (2018) that the use of technology in education is crucial to achieving the intended learning objectives and supports increased student involvement. Similar to the research conducted by Rasheed et al. (2020), the integration of technology in the classroom is considered an essential facet of blended learning.

In this study, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was employed to evaluate the student's satisfaction levels and behavioral intention in utilizing Google Classroom within a Statistics class. The findings of the study unveiled that students express satisfaction with the integration of Google Classroom in their statistics class. Similarly, Keengwe and Georgina (2012) claimed technological Advancements have led to significant changes in education delivery for it easily delivers the information they need, also this is comparable to the study of Azhar and Iqbal (2018) in that it allows professors and students to communicate easily even outside of the classroom. In addition, Google Classroom integration helps in accomplishing more tasks and has become part of their valuable

learning experience. Similar to the study of Saadé and Bahli (2005) these two elements affect the intention of the user to utilize and adopt the technology. According to Wijaya (2016), the perceived ease of use affects usability when they feel comfortable and do not need much effort to use the technology. This has resulted in a new trend in education where increased technological use is considered an acceptable medium of instruction.

Conclusions

The findings of the study revealed that Google Classroom is one of the key factors in today's blended learning environment. The user-friendly design of Google Classroom makes it easy to administer and engage in statistics classes. The platform ensures that sharing statistical data, and infographics, or accessing assignments related to statistical ideas is easy for users.

Using statistics courses on Google Classroom has shown to be a revolutionary teaching strategy. In terms of perceived usefulness, the platform's real-time communication, collaborative learning tools, and effective assignment management greatly improve the learning process as a whole. The ability to attend lessons from anywhere is advantageous to students as it allows them to overcome time and geographical limitations. The availability of materials via online platforms, such as datasets and statistical tools, enhances the educational process and adds to the overall quality of the learning process.

The perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of Google Classroom have a significant influence on the behavioral intention to utilize it. Users tend to accept and utilize technology when they feel it is easy to use and provides academic benefits, therefore, students are more likely to adopt it.

Recommendations

Detailed training is necessary for teachers and students to fully grasp Google Classroom's features to use it effectively in engineering education. Educators are encouraged to have a dynamic and inclusive blended learning environment through collaborative learning well-organized course content, clear communication norms, and integration with Google Workspace features.

Teachers and students need to be familiar with the features of the Google Classroom platform to improve the perceived ease of use of the program. To improve the perceived ease of use for all users and establish a user-friendly learning environment, it is advised that students support one another when navigating the platform.

To optimize the usefulness of Google Classroom in a statistics class, it is imperative to highlight the perceived uses of the platform and guarantee the availability of easily accessible teaching resources to facilitate users in obtaining their academic goals. This

will ultimately elevate the overall quality of the educational experience within the Google Classroom setting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The research protocol was approved by the Quezon City University Research Ethics Board which includes compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, the anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents were not exposed to any form of harm, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to express sincere gratitude to the College of Engineering of Quezon City University for the motivation and support they have given to finish this study and to other contributors for their guidance in constructing the survey instrument.

REFERENCES

- Alim, N., Linda, W., Gunawan, F., & Saad, M. S. M. (2019). The effectiveness of Google classroom as an instructional media: A case of state islamic institute of Kendari, Indonesia. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 7(2), 240-246.
- Azhar, K. A., & Iqbal, N. (2018). Effectiveness of Google classroom: Teachers' perceptions. *Prizren Social Science Journal*, 2(2), 52.
- Hwang, G.-J., Lai, C.-L., & Wang, S.-Y. (2015). Seamless flipped learning: a mobile technology-enhanced flipped classroom with effective learning strategies. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 2(4), 449–473. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-015-0043-0>
- Keengwe, J., & Georgina, D. (2012). The digital course training workshop for online learning and teaching. *Education and Information Technologies*, 17, 365-379.
- Kumar, J. A., Bervell, B., & Osman, S. (2020). Google classroom: insights from Malaysian higher education students' and instructors' experiences. *Education and information technologies*, 25, 4175-4195.
- Mafa, K. R. (2018). Capabilities of Google Classroom as a teaching and learning tool in higher education. *International Journal of Science Technology & Engineering*, 5(5), 30-34.
- Mohammadi, H. (2015). Factors affecting the e-learning outcomes: An integration of TAM and IS success model (Retration of vol 32, pg 701, 2015). *Telematics and Informatics*, 32(4), R1-R1.
- Northey, G., Govind, R., Bucic, T., Chylinski, M., Dolan, R., & van Esch, P. (2018). The effect of "here and now" learning on student engagement and academic achievement. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 49(2), 321-333.
- Omar, N., Munir, Z. A., Kaizan, F. Q., Noranee, S., & Malik, S. A. (2019). The Impact of Employees Motivation, Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use on

- Employee Performance among Selected Public Sector Employees. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 9(6), 1128-1139.
- Rasheed, R. A., Kamsin, A., & Abdullah, N. A. (2020). Challenges in the online component of blended learning: A systematic review. *Computers & Education*, 144, 103701.
- Saadé, R., & Bahli, B. (2005). The impact of cognitive absorption on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use in on-line learning: an extension of the technology acceptance model. *Information & management*, 42(2), 317-327.
- Santos, J. M. (2021). Google Classroom: beyond the traditional setting. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 79(4), 626-639.
- Shaharane, Mohd, I. N., Jamil, J., & Mohamad Rodzi, S. S. (2016). The application of Google Classroom as a tool for teaching and learning. *Journal of Telecommunication, Electronic and Computer Engineering*, 8(10), 5-8.
- Zuñiga-Tonio, J. (2021). Google Classroom as a tool of support for flexible learning in the new normal. *Journal of Education, Management and Development Studies*, 1(2), 25-39.